

Radio Mean Labelling for the Pendant Graph Family

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Abstract: Here, labeling a graph is simply plugging numbers (integers) into the vertices, edges, or both in a particular graph. Here we only focus on the vertex labeling. The idea of radio mean labeling is one of the most ubiquitous fields of graph labeling. Radio labeling is a function f of G which is a labeling that can be defined by the following inequality $|f(u) - f(v)| \geq \text{diam}(G) + 1 - d(u, v)$; $u, v \in V(G)$ where $d(u, v)$; the distance between any two vertices. After completing the particular assignment (this should be the minimum assignment to satisfy the equal condition of the above function), the integer that spans the labeling is known to be the radio mean number or radio number. The notation radio mean number represents the minimum span of a radio labeling for. The purpose of this project is to present a general proof for the radio mean number of pendant graphs. The cycle takes the Corona product with a complete graph of 1 where pendant graph are a subset of Corona. A generalized equation must be obtained in order to obtain the radio mean number. Because the cycle and the diameter have odd and even variants, we must treat them separately. We focus on both cases here in the hopes of expanding them to the entire family and then to the larger case of Corona by defining a general equation that can take the radio mean number for that case.

Keywords: Diameter, Pendant graphs, Radio mean labeling, Radio mean number

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Introduction

In this project, we are exploring graph theory, graph labeling, and their applications. Graph theory is the area of mathematics that studies objects called graphs. The first theory of graphs goes back to 1736 and the first textbook came about in 1958 but most of the work within this field is only a few decades old. Graph labeling is a mapping that sends some set of graph elements to a set of numbers or colors. If we label both vertices and edges, then the labeling is called total labeling. Label graphs are becoming an increasingly useful family of mathematical models for a broad range of applications. Here we only focus on vertex labeling. In vertex labeling, the Channel assignment problem [6] is one of the most prioritized applications. There are two types of channel assignment strategies, namely fixed and dynamic. In fixed channel assignment, every cell is given a fixed set of channels in which it can transmit and receive data. If a call is made and all the channels that are available to the cells are preoccupied then the call may go blocked. The second type of channel assignment strategy is dynamic channel assignment. Here, the cells are not given a predefined set of channels. Instead, the channel is provided on demand. The advantage here is because the channels are allocated on a demand

basis the probability of block king of a call is reduced. Here the computational load on the MSC increases very much. Therefore, interference occurs. Regarding this matter, Radio mean labeling came to the place. Since this is moving with a very important real-world application, we were very much motivated to work on the radio mean number of particular graph families.

Research Methodology

This section will introduce the basic information and notations needed to understand our work.

Preliminaries

Graph is a mathematical representation of a network and it describes the relationship between lines and points. A graph consists of some points and lines between them. The length of the lines and the position of the points do not matter. Each object in a graph is called a node.

Graph theory: It is a sub-field of mathematics that deals with graphs: diagrams that involve points and lines and which often pictorially represent mathematical truths. Graph theory is the study of the relationship between edges and vertices. Formally, a graph is a pair (V, E) , where V is a finite set of vertices and E is a finite set of edges.

The diameter of a graph is the length of the shortest path between the most distanced nodes. The diameter measures the extent of a graph and the topological length between two nodes.

Graph labeling is an assignment of integers to the vertices or edges, or both, subject to certain conditions.

The corona $G_1 \odot G_2$ of graphs G_1 and G_2 is the graph obtained by taking one copy of G_1 , which has P_1 vertices, and P_1 copies of G_2 , and then joining the i^{th} vertex of G_1 by an edge to every vertex in the i^{th} copy of G_2 . *Invalid source specified.*

The pendant graph is a corona of the form $C_n \odot K_1$ where $n \geq 3$. *Invalid source specified.* [3]

Result and discussion

Here first we must do the manual labeling for the simpler cases and extend that to some higher-order cases. And finally, we must derive general equations using some patterns. The following theorems give us the radio mean number for the pendant graph family.

Theorem 1 $rmn(C_{2n} \odot K_1) = \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{4} \right\rfloor \right) * (n - 2) \right] + 7$, where C_{2n} is an even cycle, $n \geq 2$.

Theorem 2 $rmn(C_{2n+1} \odot K_1) = \left\{ \left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor + \frac{7}{2} - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{4} \right\rfloor \right) * 2 \left\lfloor \frac{n-2}{2} \right\rfloor \right\} + 3$, where C_{2n+1} is an odd cycle, $n \geq 1$.

Fig.1: The graph of $C_6 \odot K_1$

$$\begin{aligned}
 rmn(C_6 \odot K_1) &= \left[\left(\frac{6}{2} + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{6}{4} \right\rfloor \right) * (6 - 2) \right] + 7 \\
 &= [(3 + 4 - [1.5]) * 4] + 7 \\
 &= (5 * 4) + 7 \\
 &= 27
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig.2: The graph of $C_3 \odot K_1$

$$\begin{aligned}
 rmn(C_3 \odot K_1) &= \left(\left\lfloor \frac{3}{2} \right\rfloor + \frac{7}{2} - \left\lfloor \frac{3}{4} \right\rfloor \right) * 2 \left\lfloor \frac{3-2}{2} \right\rfloor + 3 \\
 &= 10
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof

Theorem 1

Case I (Pendant graphs which have an even cycle with odd diameter.)

Let us prove this by combinatorial methods.

Consider the assignment;

$$|f(v) - f(u)| \geq diam(G) + 1 - d(u, v)$$

We can rearrange this equation as follows;

$$|f(v) - f(u)| + d(u, v) \geq C[diam(G) + 1]$$

Where C is a constant.

Therefore, to have the minimum integer as the assignment the distance must be maximum.

So let us consider the outer vertices first. (Since they have a greater distance)

If we connect outside vertices by imaginary lines, we will get a cycle that is homotopic equivalent to the inner cycle. So, we must consider two cycles and connect them.

Consider the diameter of the whole graph is d and C_{2n} with odd diameter $\bar{d} = d - 2$.

Choose a vertex and assign it the label 0 .

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance of diameter. i.e., \bar{d} from the previously assigned vertex and assign it the label $\bar{d} + 1 - \bar{d} = 1$

$$\begin{aligned} (\because |f(v) - f(u)| &\geq \text{diam}(C_{2n}) + 1 - d(u, v)) \\ f(v) &\geq \bar{d} + 1 - \bar{d} + f(u) \text{ [which is 0]} \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $\left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor$ from the previously assigned vertex assign the label

$$\bar{d} + 1 + 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor = \bar{d} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor \text{ to the vertex.}$$

Now choose a vertex at a distance \bar{d} from the last labeled vertex and assign the label

$$(\bar{d} + 1 - \bar{d}) + \bar{d} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor = \bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor \text{ to the vertex.}$$

Further, choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $\left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor$ from the vertex, and assign it the label

$$(\bar{d} + 1 - \bar{d}) + \bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor = \bar{d} + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor \text{ to the vertex.}$$

Continuing in this manner we see that the labels are

$$0, 1, \bar{d} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor, \bar{d} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor + 1, 2 \left(\bar{d} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor \right), 2 \left(\bar{d} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 1, \dots$$

Continuing in this way, the label assigned to the second last vertex is $\left(\bar{d} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor \right) * (\bar{d} - 1)$.

And the label assigned to the last vertex is $\left[\left(\bar{d} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor \right) * (\bar{d} - 1) \right] + 1$.

$$\text{Hence, } C_{2n} = \left[\left(\bar{d} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}}{2} \right\rfloor \right) * (\bar{d} - 1) \right] + 1$$

By considering corresponding n vertices by diameter $\bar{d} = \frac{n}{2}$.

We can derive the following:

$$C_{2n} = \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{4} \right\rfloor \right) * \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right) \right] + 1 \quad (1) \quad [4]$$

Our next step is to combine outer vertices with the inner cycle.

To get the idea of combining these two, first, let us consider a simpler case. i.e., a cycle with 2 vertices added to its diagonal. As mentioned above to get the maximum distance we must consider these newly added vertices and label them as 0 and 1. Then chose a vertex at a distance $d - 1$. Here we consider the diameter of the whole graph.

Then the required assignment will be

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 1) + f(u) \\ &= d + 1 - d + 1 + 1 \\ &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

After we come to the inner cycle, we can follow a similar method by assigning interns to the corresponding vertices as follows.

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $d - 2$ from the previously assigned vertex and assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 2) + 3 \\ &= 6 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $\left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil$ from the previously assigned vertex assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil + 6 \\ &= d + 7 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \\ &= \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $d - 2$ from the previously assigned vertex and assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 2) + \left\{ \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \right\} \\ &= \left[\left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $\left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil$ from the previously assigned vertex assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil + \left\{ \left[\left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \right\} \\ &= 2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $d - 2$ from the previously assigned vertex and assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 2) + \left\{ 2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \right\} \\ &= \left[2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $\left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil$ from the previously assigned vertex assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil + \left\{ \left[2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \right\} \\ &= 3 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $d - 2$ from the previously assigned vertex and assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 2) + \left\{ 3 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \right\} \\ &= \left[3 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\left[\left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) * (d - 3) \right] + 6$$

∴ vertices of an even cycle = $2d - 2$

Our equation becomes,

$$\begin{aligned} &\left\{ \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 2 \right) + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{\left(\frac{n}{2} + 2 \right) - 2}{2} \right\rceil \right] * \left(\frac{n}{2} + 2 - 3 \right) \right\} + 6 \\ &\left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 6 - \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil \right) * \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right) \right] + 6 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Note that this equation only includes two outside vertices. But in our general case, we have much more vertices to deal with. Therefore, we must combine the equation of the outside imaginary cycle with this equation ((1) + (2)).

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 6 - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{4} \right\rfloor \right) * \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right) \right] + 6 + \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{4} \right\rfloor \right) * \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right) \right] + 1 \\ &= 7 + \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right) \left[\frac{n}{2} + 6 - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{4} \right\rfloor + \frac{n}{2} + 2 - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{4} \right\rfloor \right] \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{4} \right\rfloor \right) * (n-2) \right] + 7 \end{aligned}$$

This is the general equation of the radio mean number of pendant graphs which has an even cycle with an odd diameter.

Case II (Pendant graphs that have an even cycle with an even diameter.)

Consider the diameter of the whole graph is d and C_{2n} having an even diameter $\bar{d} = d - 2$.

Select a vertex, then give it the label "0".

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a diameter distance. i.e., \bar{d} from the previously allocated vertex and label it $\bar{d} + 1 - \bar{d} = 1$

$$\begin{aligned} (\because |f(v) - f(u)| &\geq \text{diam}(C_{2n}) + 1 - d(u, v)) \\ f(v) &\geq \bar{d} + 1 - \bar{d} + f(u) \text{ [which is 0]} \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex $\left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor$ distance from the last allocated vertex and label it.

$$\bar{d} + 1 + 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor + 1 = \bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor .$$

Now Choose a vertex \bar{d} distance from the last labeled vertex and label it.

$$(\bar{d} + 1 - \bar{d}) + \bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor = \bar{d} + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor .$$

Furthermore, choose an unlabeled vertex $\left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor$ distance away from the vertex and label it.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\bar{d} + 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + \bar{d} + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor + 1 \\ &= 2\bar{d} + 6 - 2 \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor . \end{aligned}$$

Continuing in this way we can take the labels as follows

$$0, 1, \bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor, \bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor + 1, 2 \left(\bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor \right), 2 \left(\bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 1, \dots$$

Continuing in this way, the label for the second-to-last vertex is $\left(\bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) * (\bar{d} - 1)$.

And also, the label for the last vertex is $\left[\left(\bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) * (\bar{d} - 1) \right] + 1$.

$$\text{Hence, } C_{2n} = \left[\left(\bar{d} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{\bar{d}+1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) * (\bar{d} - 1) \right] + 1$$

By considering corresponding n vertices by diameter $\bar{d} = \frac{n}{2}$.

We can derive the following:

$$C_{2n} = \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{n+1}{4} \right\rfloor \right) * \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right) \right] + 1 \quad (3) \quad [4]$$

Our next step is to combine outer vertices with the inner cycle.

To get the idea of combining these two, first, let us consider a simpler case. i.e., a cycle with 2 vertices added to its diagonal. As mentioned above to get the maximum distance we must consider these newly added vertices and label them as 0 and 1. Then select a vertex at $d - 1$ distance. Here we consider the diameter of the whole graph.

Then the required assignment will be

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 1) + f(u) \\ &= d + 1 - d + 1 + 1 \\ &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

After we come to the inner cycle, we can follow a similar method by assigning integers to the corresponding vertices as follows.

Choose an unlabeled vertex $d - 2$ distance from the last allocated vertex and label it;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 2) + 3 \\ &= 6 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex $\left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor$ distance from the last allocated vertex and label it;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor + 6 \\ &= d + 7 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor \\ &= \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex $d - 2$ distance from the last allocated vertex and label it;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 2) + \left\{ \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right\} \\ &= \left[\left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex $\left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor$ distance from the last allocated vertex and label it;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor + \left\{ \left[\left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \right\} \\ &= 2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Select an unlabeled vertex at a distance $d - 2$ from the last assigned vertex and assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 2) + \left\{ 2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right\} \\ &= \left[2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Select an unlabeled vertex at a distance $\left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor$ from the last assigned vertex and assign the label;

$$f(v) = d + 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor + \left\{ \left[2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \right\}$$

$$= 3 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3$$

Select an unlabeled vertex at a distance $d - 2$ from the last assigned vertex and assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 2) + \left\{ 3 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \right\} \\ &= \left[3 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Continuing in this manner we see that the labels are

$$3, 6, \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3, 2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3, 3 \left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rceil \right) + 3, \dots$$

Continuing in this way, the label for the last vertex is $\left[\left(d + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rceil \right) * (d - 3) \right] + 6$

\therefore vertices of an even cycle = $2d - 2$

Our equation becomes,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\{ \left(\frac{n}{2} + 2 \right) + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{\left(\frac{n}{2} + 2 \right) - 1}{2} \right\rceil * \left(\frac{n}{2} + 2 - 3 \right) \right\} + 6 \\ & \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 6 - \left\lceil \frac{n+2}{4} \right\rceil \right) * \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right) \right] + 6 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Note that this equation only includes two outside vertices. But in our general case, we have much more vertices to deal with. Therefore, we must combine the equation of the outside imaginary cycle with this equation ((3) + (4)).

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 3 - \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{4} \right\rceil \right) * \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right) \right] + 1 + \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 6 - \left\lceil \frac{n+2}{4} \right\rceil \right) * \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right) \right] + 6 \\ & = \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right) \left[n - \left\lceil \frac{n+2}{4} \right\rceil - \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{4} \right\rceil \right] + 7 \end{aligned}$$

By using ceiling function properties;

$$\begin{aligned} & = (n - 2) \left[\frac{n}{2} + \frac{9}{2} - \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil - \frac{1}{2} \right] + 7 \\ & = \left[\left(\frac{n}{2} + 4 - \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil \right) * (n - 2) \right] + 7 \end{aligned}$$

This is the general equation of the radio mean number of pendant graphs which has an even cycle with an even diameter.

Theorem 2

Let us prove this by combinatorial methods.

Consider the assignment, $|f(v) - f(u)| \geq diam(G) + 1 - d(u, v)$.

We can rearrange this equation: $|f(v) - f(u)| + d(u, v) \geq C[diam(G) + 1]$; where C is a constant.

Therefore, to have the minimum integer as the assignment the distance must be maximum. So let us consider the outer vertices first. (Since they have a greater distance). If we connect outside vertices by imaginary lines, we will get a cycle

that is homotopic equivalent to the inner cycle. So, we must consider two cycles and connect them. Consider the diameter of the whole graph is d and C_{2n+1} with diameter, $\bar{d} = d - 2$.

$$C_{2n+1} = \left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{n+1}{4} \right\rfloor \right) * \left\lfloor \frac{n-2}{2} \right\rfloor \quad (5) \text{ (Merlin, 2018).}$$

Our next step is to combine outer vertices with the inner cycle. To get the idea of combining these two, first, let us consider a simpler case. i.e., a cycle with 2 vertices added to its two vertices apart from \bar{d} distance. As mentioned above to get the maximum distance we must consider these newly added vertices and label them as 0 and 1. Then chose a vertex at a distance $d - 1$ (the only difference between the cycles having even diameters is we start the assignment on the one vertex in an inside cycle and follow the same procedure). Here we consider the diameter of the whole graph. Then the required assignment will be; $f(v) = d + 1 - (d - 1) + f(u) = d + 1 - d + 1 + 1 = 3$. After we come to the inner cycle, we can follow a similar method by assigning integers to the corresponding vertices as follows. Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $d - 2$ from the previously assigned vertex and assign the label; $f(v) = d + 1 - (d - 2) + 3 = 6$. Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $\left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor$ from the previously assigned vertex assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor + 6 \\ &= d + 7 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor \\ &= \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $d - 2$ from the previously assigned vertex and assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 2) + \left\{ \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right\} \\ &= \left[\left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $\left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor$ from the previously assigned vertex assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor + \left\{ \left[\left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \right\} \\ &= 2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $d - 2$ from the previously assigned vertex and assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - (d - 2) + \left\{ 2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right\} \\ &= \left[2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Choose an unlabeled vertex at a distance $\left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor$ from the previously assigned vertex assign the label;

$$\begin{aligned} f(v) &= d + 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor + \left\{ \left[2 \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \right] + 3 \right\} \\ &= 3 \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor \right) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

Continuing in this manner we see that the labels are

$$3, 6, \left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor\right) + 3, 2\left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor\right) + 3, 3\left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor\right) + 3, \dots$$

Continuing in this way, the label assigned to the last vertex is $\left[\left(d + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{d-2}{2} \right\rfloor\right) * (d - 3)\right] + 3$

$$\therefore \text{vertices of an odd cycle} = 2d - 1$$

Our equation becomes, $\left\{\left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor + 2\right) + 4 - \left\lfloor \frac{\left(\frac{n}{2} + 2\right) - 2}{2} \right\rfloor * \left(\frac{n}{2} + 2 - 3\right)\right\} + 3$. To have an integer assignment we can derive an equation from above as follows:

$$\left\{\left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor + \frac{11}{2}\right) * 2 \left\lfloor \frac{n-2}{2} \right\rfloor\right\} + 3 \tag{6}$$

Note that this equation only includes two outside vertices. But in our general case, we have much more vertices to deal with. Therefore, we must combine the equation of the outside imaginary cycle with this equation ((5) + (6)).

$$\begin{aligned} &\left\{\left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor + 3 - \left\lfloor \frac{n+1}{4} \right\rfloor\right) * \left\lfloor \frac{n-2}{2} \right\rfloor\right\} + \left\{\left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor + \frac{11}{2}\right) * 2 \left\lfloor \frac{n-2}{2} \right\rfloor + 3\right\} \\ &= \left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor + \frac{7}{2} - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{4} \right\rfloor\right) * 2 \left\lfloor \frac{n-2}{2} \right\rfloor + 3 \end{aligned}$$

This is the general equation of the radio mean number of pendant graphs which has odd cycles.

Conclusion

The radio mean number for pendant graphs. Radio mean labeling and radio mean number is one of the most important cases in vertex labeling. As we all know there are so many applications in graph theory [5]. The major reason is we can find graphs anywhere. Whenever we have two nodes and a line, we can derive a graph. Similarly for radio mean labeling, there are so many applications namely, channel assignment problems, radar transmissions, cryptography, astronomy, circuit design, etc. Here we mainly focused on the interference or signal loss of GSM channels. We all experience this one, while we move, we experience various signal strengths. Sometimes in the same house for different areas, we are having different signal strengths. Because whenever the distance comes to place, interference occurs. So, we must reduce that or eliminate it. To do that we must assign accurate power or signal strength to the towers. But we can't expect that the signal towers or network towers are planted according to a graph family that we have already worked on. What we can do is clarify the patterns and the graphs. Since there are so many graphs and graph families, we have to have more brains here. So, we warmly welcome all of you to come down to the area and stand with all the cases someday.

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References

- [1] A. Graf, "Gracefull labelings of pendant graphs," *Rose-Hulman Undergraduate Mathematics Journal*, pp. 15(1), 158-172, 2014.
- [2] N. L. Prasanna, "Applications of Graph Labeling in Communication Networks," *Oriental Journal of Computer Science and Technology*, p. 7(1), 2014.

- [3] K. M. P. G. S. C. & P. A. A. I. Kapuhennayake, "An alternative approach for the anti-magic labelling of a wheel graph and a pendant graph.," *JSc EUSL*, pp. 12(2), 47-60., 2021.
- [4] E. T. & M. T. A. Merlin, "Radio number of cycles and their total graphs," *World Scientific News*, pp. 101, 55-64., 2018.
- [5] R. S. Ponraja, "Radio mean labeling of a graph," *AKCE International Journal of Graphs and Combinatorics*, pp. 12, 224-228., 2015.
- [6] H. .W.K., "Fequency assignment: theory and application," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, p. 68(12), 1980.

